

TWENTY-THIRD INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS (ICCM23)

Correlation of the Permeability of Carbon/Carbon Composites with the Porosity during the Carbonization Process

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Project Overview

Project Goal

- Optimization of the densification process of Carbon/Carbon composites.

Presented Work

- Development of novel technique for the evaluation of permeability and porosity from one experiment.
- Correlation of permeability and porosity of Carbon/Carbon composites.

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Outline

1. Introduction: densification of Carbon/Carbon composites
2. Pyrolysis schedules and materials
3. Permeability of Carbon/Carbon composites
 - Pulse-decay experiment
4. Porosity of Carbon/Carbon composites
 - Micro-computed tomography
 - Pycnometry
5. Correlation of permeability and porosity
6. Prediction of porosity from pulse-decay experiment
 - Quasi-steady state model

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Densification of Carbon/Carbon Composites

Manufacturing of Carbon/Carbon Composites

Matrix Degradation → Shrinkage and Weight Loss

Densification Process

- Repetition Infiltration/Pyrolysis.
- Takes several months to complete.

Densification process: Muhammed et al. 2021 *J. Mater. Sci.* DOI 10.1007/s10853-021-06401-3

Optimization of Densification

Reduce Densification Time

Tailor Porosity Development with Pyrolysis Schedule

Select Best Parameters for Re-Infiltration

Injection

Correlation of permeability with porosity

Void growth: Muhammed et al. 2023 *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*

Optimization of pyrolysis schedule: Muhammed et al. 2023 *Ceram. Int.* DOI 10.1016/j.ceramint.2023.03.121

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Pyrolysis Schedules and Kinetics of the Reactions

Kinetics of reaction: Muhammed et al. 2022 *J. Mater. Sci.* DOI 10.1007/s10853-022-08007-9

Materials

Laminates

- Matrix precursor → Benzoxazine resin
- Carbon fabric

Samples of Different Thicknesses

- Laminates of 5 plies → 2.1 mm thickness
- Laminates of 33 plies → 12.3 mm thickness

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Permeability of Carbon/Carbon Composites

Structure of Carbon/Carbon Composites

- Flow monitoring experiments not trivial.
- Pulse-decay experiments with air easy and reliable.

Pulse-Decay Experiment for Composites Characterization

- Air evacuation process in sandwich composites¹.
- Effects of lay-up process parameters and post-processing in AFP composites².

¹ Cender et al. *J. Compos. Mater.* 2022 DOI 10.1177/00219983221115824

² Karimi et al. *J. Reinf. Plast.* 2023 DOI 10.1177/07316844231166078

Pulse-Decay Experiment for Air Permeability

Through-the-thickness experimental set-up for the measurement of air flow

Pressure Decay Curves and Numerical Simulations

- Pressure decays over time: shape of curve depends on unknowns K_i/ϕ and b .
- Generate numerical curve by solving Eq. 1 (non-dimensional form) while optimizing K_i/ϕ and b .

b : Klinkenberg parameter, function of pore diameter only
 K_i : intrinsic permeability K_g : permeability to gas
 V_R : volume of reservoir A : cross-section of core

$$(1) \quad \frac{\partial P}{\partial t} = \frac{K_i}{\phi \mu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left((P + b) \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} \right)$$

$$(2) \quad K_g = K_i \left(1 + \frac{b}{P} \right)$$

Figure \hat{P} vs \hat{t} : Cender et al. *Transport in Porous Media* 2016 (115) 541-562 DOI 10.1007/s11242-016-0784-x

Permeability of Carbon/Carbon Composites – 5 Plies

Permeability of Carbon/Carbon Composites – 33 Plies

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Porosity: X-Ray Computed Tomography

- Otsu's segmentation for the identification of open and closed porosity.
- Possibility to monitor microstructure of same samples tested for permeability.
- Resolution: 90 voxels and 6 voxels (limit on visible pores).

$$\phi_{tot} = \frac{V_{tot}}{V_{sample}}$$

$$\phi_{conn} = \frac{V_{conn}}{V_{sample}}$$

V_{tot} : total volume of pores

V_{conn} : volume of connected porosity through-the-thickness

V_{sample} : $l \cdot h \cdot w$

Porosity: Pycnometry

- Measuring gases: Helium and Nitrogen.
- Nitrogen → to measure open porosity.
- Helium → diffuses into closed pores.

Comparison Helium and Nitrogen

- Evaluate open and closed porosity

$$V_{sample} = V_{sample\ chamber} - \frac{V_{ref.\ chamber}}{\frac{P_1}{P_2} - 1}$$

Porosity of Carbon/Carbon Composites – 5 Plies

$$\phi_{conn} = \frac{V_{conn}}{V_{sample}}$$

V_{conn} : measured volume of pores connected through-the-thickness (from CT)

V_{sample} : $l \cdot h \cdot w$

Porosity of Carbon/Carbon Composites – 33 Plies

$$\phi_{conn} = \frac{V_{conn}}{V_{sample}}$$

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Correlation of Permeability and Porosity – 5 Plies

Correlation of Permeability and Porosity – 33 Plies

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Porosity Predictions: Quasi-Steady State Model

- Small density change in reservoir → **Quasi-steady state analysis.**

$$K_{is} = - \frac{2\mu_g L_R L_S}{P^2(t) + 2bP(t)} \frac{\partial P}{\partial t}$$

μ_g : gas viscosity

L_R : characteristic length reservoir

L_S : characteristic length sample b : Klinkenberg parameter

K_{is} : quasi-steady intrinsic liquid permeability

- Model is valid in interval of constant $\frac{1}{P^2(t)+2bP(t)} \frac{\partial P}{\partial t}$

- Model is applied to pressure decay curves.
- Porosity is predicted by comparing K_i/ϕ with K_{is} .

Porosity Predictions with Quasi-Steady Permeability: 5 Plies

..... Sample A5 - Dwell 250C — Sample A5 - Dwell 350C
— Sample B5 — Sample C5

Sample	$\frac{K_t}{\phi}$ [m ²]	K_{is} [m ²]	Predicted ϕ
Sample A ₅ Dwell 350	5.7E-15	5.7E-16	10.0%
Sample B ₅	1.6E-13	3.2E-14	20.00%
Sample C ₅	1.3E-13	2.7E-14	20.80%

Porosity Predictions with Quasi-Steady Permeability: 33 Plies

..... Sample A₃₃ - Dwell 250C — Sample A₃₃ - Dwell 350C
— Sample C₃₃ — Sample B₃₃

Sample	$\frac{K_t}{\phi}$ [m ²]	K_{is} [m ²]	Predicted ϕ
Sample A ₃₃ Dwell 350	2.1E-15	2.0E-16	9.4%
Sample B ₃₃	3.0E-13	6.2E-14	20.60%
Sample C ₃₃	1.4E-13	2.7E-14	19.30%

Conclusions

Pulse-decay test for Carbon/Carbon composites

- One experiment to measure both permeability and porosity.
- Time savings: CT and pycnometry measurements not needed.

Correlation of permeability and porosity

- Basis for simulations for optimization of pyrolysis and re-infiltration.

Future Works

- Simulations of gas evacuation during pyrolysis.
- Simulations of re-infiltration process (RTM).
 - Numerical mesh extrapolated from CT scan of physical samples.

Our journal publications on Carbon/Carbon composites

- **Densification Process**

F. Muhammed, T. Lavaggi, S. Advani, M. Mirotznik, J.W. Gillespie, *Journal of Materials Science* (2021) 56(32):17877–17914
“Influence of material and process parameters on microstructure evolution during the fabrication of carbon-carbon composites: a review”

- **Kinetics of Degradation Reactions**

F. Muhammed, L. Moretti, T. Lavaggi, C. Lam, T. Tao, S. Advani, J.W. Gillespie *Journal of Materials Science* (2022) 57:21915–21934
“Influence of pyrolytic decomposition on the microstructure evolution of benzoxazine-derived carbon-carbon composites”

- **Optimization of Pyrolyzing Schedule**

F. Muhammed, T. Lavaggi, L. Moretti, S. Advani, J.W. Gillespie, *Ceramics International* (2023) 49(12):19996-20006
“Pyrolysis schedule optimization of benzoxazine-derived carbon/carbon composites through reaction rate optimization”

- **Void Growth and Glass Transition Temperature during Pyrolysis**

F. Muhammed, T. Lavaggi, S. Advani, J.W. Gillespie, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* (2023)
“Relating the microstructural and glass transition temperature evolution of a carbon-carbon composite precursor during pyrolysis using thermomechanical analysis”

Thank you!

Questions?